

ISSN 2957-2169

DOI:

مركز مطالعات حقوق بين الملل ايران

The Psychological and Social Challenges of Refugees in Host Countries: A Focus on Recent Violence in Germany

Nasim Amiri Ghadi ¹, Amirali R. Davoudpour ²

- 1- Faculty of Anthropology and Cultural Studies, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan-Poland
- 2- Iranian Canon of Medicine and Law, Administrative Wing of Law and Healing Association, Iranian Watchdog of Medicine and Law, Tehran-Iran

Email of the corresponding author: davoudpour@canmedlaw.org

Accepted and published August, 2024

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Abstract

Migration, especially forced migration as seen with refugees, presents significant psychological and social challenges. Countries such as Germany and France have become primary destinations for refugees from war-torn or economically struggling regions like the Middle East. Many refugees arrive hoping for a better life, while some also seek governmental assistance. However, after facing hardships during their journey, refugees often experience psychological distress due to the lack of social integration, unemployment, and a sense of rejection by their host societies. This article explores the root causes of these challenges and the impact on both refugees and host communities, drawing attention to the rise of psychological disorders, societal disintegration, and the necessity for psychological intervention and social support systems. Current violent incidents requires general attention to the mental health and Psychology of the refugees especially with regards to the course of their labor, financial and integration processes.

Keywords: Migration, Integration, Psychology

Introduction

Germany, along with other European Union countries like France, has welcomed a large number of refugees, especially from countries facing war, political unrest, and economic instability such as Afghanistan and Syria. However, this wave of migration, which refugees often see as a path to a better life, frequently leads to unforeseen psychological and social challenges. Many refugees endure difficult journeys, only to find themselves struggling with depression and severe mental health disorders upon arrival. These problems are often compounded by the refugees' lack of social belonging and the complex integration processes in the host countries (Klapproth et al., 2021).

The Psychological Impact of Refugee Migration

Refugees face multifaceted psychological challenges that can emerge from a variety of factors. Among these are the feelings of rejection by the host society, the lack of employment opportunities, and the stressful living conditions in multicultural camps (Silove et al., 2017). Additionally, the progressive loss of freedom and autonomy that many refugees experience, particularly when comparing their current situation with the authoritarian structures of their home countries, can lead to mental health issues such as depression and anxiety. This psychological deterioration often becomes evident over time and can lead to chronic mental health problems (Fazel et al., 2012).

Refugees, who have no sense of ownership over their new country, often find themselves marginalized and excluded from societal structures. The common rhetoric, "Go back to where you came from," further deepens their sense of alienation and insecurity. In such environments, it is difficult for refugees to achieve psychological and social stability, which contributes to long-term mental health issues, including self-harm and harm to others (Schweitzer et al., 2011). Notable examples include incidents like the case of an Iranian couple in Canada (Davoudpur, A.R., 2024) and the violent attacks in the city of Solingen, Germany (Measham et al., 2001).

Social Disintegration and Anomie

An additional social phenomenon faced by refugees in host countries is the breakdown of familial, ethical, and psychological structures. Some individuals actively participate in the disintegration of these foundations, leading to a rise in social disorder and deviant behavior. Social media plays a significant role in this, with figures such as Instagram influencers or online personalities engaging in political activism that destabilizes both their host and home countries. In addition to political amateurs and trolls, online spaces have also become breeding grounds for encouraging illegal migration, currency outflows, and investment in real estate in countries like Dubai, Cyprus, and Turkey (Sas et al., 2020).

Denying the existence of economic, social, political, and psychological pressures in the Middle East is misleading. Structural flaws in these regions, compounded by sanctions, nascent governments, and harsh laws, create an environment that encourages migration. Refugees leaving these countries are not merely escaping war but also a myriad of systemic issues that cannot be resolved with simple theoretical frameworks or television propaganda (Almoshmash, 2016).

The Role of Psychotherapy and Social Support

The psychological diseases that arise among refugees often go untreated. Many refugees do not seek medical help, resulting in the progressive deterioration of their mental health. This untreated mental distress threatens the fundamental social units of society, such as families and communities, and can ultimately lead to the destruction of entire nations (Silove et al., 2017).

It is essential to acknowledge that migration is not a guarantee of happiness. On the contrary, it often results in varying degrees of psychological trauma. Regardless of whether a refugee is Afghan, Iranian, or Syrian, the act of seeking asylum often initiates a process of psychological decline that, if left unchecked, can lead to severe depression and other mental health disorders. However, with timely and appropriate psychotherapeutic intervention, the severity and manifestation of these disorders can be mitigated, providing

refugees with the tools to rebuild their lives in a healthy and productive manner (Fazel et al., 2012).

Conclusion

Psychotherapy, as a branch of psychological science, is critical in addressing the mental health crises faced by refugees. Such approaches not only aim to rehabilitate minority groups, such as refugees, but also contribute to the healing of entire nations by addressing social dysfunctions at their roots. Effective governance must involve the implementation of comprehensive mental health strategies to prevent the long-term consequences of unresolved psychological distress among refugees. By prioritizing the mental health of these vulnerable populations, host countries can mitigate the risks of social unrest and foster a more inclusive and resilient society.

Acknowledgement: Dr. Amirali R. Davoudpour is an associate professor at the Iranian Canon of Medicine and Law, a non-governmental organization dedicated to protecting the civil rights of Iranian and Afghan migrants. Nasim Amiri Ghadi is an M.A. student in the Faculty of Anthropology and Cultural Studies at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan-Poland. Both authors contributed equally to this work and claimed no conflict of interest.

References

1. Almoshmoh, N. (2016). The role of war trauma survivors in managing their own mental conditions, Syria civil war as an example. *Avicenna Journal of Medicine*, 6(3), 54–59.
2. Davoudpour, A. R. (2024a). Challenges Faced by Iranian Students and Graduates Seeking Education and Employment Abroad: An Empirical Study. *Journal of Iranian International Legal Studies*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13204120>
3. Davoudpour, A. R. (2024b). The Impact of Educational Migration on National Economies and Intellectual Property in Iran. *Journal of Iranian International Legal Studies*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13189655>
4. Fazel, M., Wheeler, J., & Danesh, J. (2012). Prevalence of serious mental disorder in 7000 refugees resettled in western countries: A systematic review. *The Lancet*, 379(9827), 1009–1014.
5. Klapproth, F., Meniño, J. R., & Sura, M. (2021). Coping with Uncertainty: Challenges for Refugees and Asylum Seekers in Germany during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 34(4), 3917–3930.
6. Measham, T., Rousseau, C., & Nadeau, L. (2001). The mental health of children of immigrant and refugee families. *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 46(7), 596–602.
7. Sas, C., Dix, A., Hartman, T., & Su, R. (2020). Migration and Digital Technologies: Impact on Society and Government. *Journal of International Communication*, 25(1), 45-62.
8. Schweitzer, R., Brough, M., Vromans, L., & Asic-Kobe, M. (2011). Mental health of newly arrived Burmese refugees in Australia: Contributions of pre-migration and post-migration experience. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 45(4), 299-307.
9. Silove, D., Steel, Z., & Watters, C. (2017). Policies of deterrence and the mental health of asylum seekers. *JAMA*, 320(3), 249-250.